

MONEY: INFLATION, ITS ECONOMIC MODELING

Hamroyev Khurshid Hamzayevich

Student of Navoi State Mining and Technological University

Mirzayeva Mavlyuda Narmuratovna

PhD, Associate professor of the department "Uzbek and foreign languages"

Navoi State Mining and Technological University

Annotation: Inflation has been known for a long time. It is assumed that it arose practically with the advent of money itself. Views on inflation of economic sciences are various. Different definitions, concepts and constructions of inflation classification are used. It seems appropriate to generalize various opinions, to propose a model of inflation and a theory of negative economic expectations, to some extent related to inflation.

Keywords: economy, money, inflation, economic science, multifactorial

The definition "inflation is an increase in the general price level" reflects only one side of inflation. modern financial and economic dictionaries characterize inflation as "the depreciation of paper money due to their release into circulation in amounts exceeding the needs of trade, which is accompanied by an increase in prices for goods ..." or "the overflow of money circulation channels with paper money in excess of real economic needs, leading to their depreciation a concrete expression of inflation is a rapid, spontaneous rise in prices", as well as "a steady increase in the average level of prices for goods and services in the economy. The phenomenon of the money market, manifested in the depreciation of paper money ... ". All these definitions associate the concept of inflation only with paper money.

Thus, inflation is a multifactorial phenomenon that reflects monetary, production and reproduction processes; violation of the balance of supply and demand of money and other proportions of the economy, expressed in an increase in the price level and an excess of money in circulation. The current inflation is

manifested not only in the fall in the purchasing power of money as the price level rises unevenly (for some goods, prices may even decrease), but also in total crisis phenomena in the state economy. Inflation is explained, in particular, by conflicting factors of production and sales, as well as by the actual money turnover, credit and financial relations. Inflation is based on an imbalance between the segments of the economy: accumulation and consumption, state revenues and expenditures, the money supply and the economy's need for money.

The most radical means of stabilizing money circulation and fighting inflation, especially after wars, revolutions and major economic crises, is monetary reform - the reorganization of monetary circulation. Monetary reform, as a rule, is a radical anti-inflationary measure aimed at stabilizing monetary circulation. Where inflation was within acceptable limits on the eve of the monetary reform, the denomination was probably called upon to complete the anti-inflationary measures of the state at this stage with the repayment of inflationary expectations. Inflationary expectations can indeed be reduced to a minimum if the monetary reform is successful. However, on the eve of the reform, the advance announcement of the denomination, in our opinion, on the contrary, slightly increased inflation expectations, which were insignificant in the first half. At the beginning of the reforms, as in any other monetary reforms, one more kind of "expectations" can be singled out, closely related to inflationary expectations and inflation itself, which the author proposes to call "assessments of the probability (expectations) of the monetary reform", and the essence, prerequisites and principles of influence on the economy of these expectations - a private theory of "estimation of the probability of monetary reform" as part of the general theory of "negative economic assessments" proposed by the author.

Thus, these are inflationary expectations that have been studied enough, and the selected expectations proposed by the author: assessments of the probability of the monetary reform; estimates of the probability (expectations) of devaluation; estimates of the probability of economic crises. All of the above estimates of

probability (expectations) are united, as follows from their name, by the negative impact on the economy, as well as the need for state intervention with the implementation of an economic policy to reduce expectations, overcome or minimize their consequences. as a rule, expectations are accompanied by a certain inflation and to a certain extent stimulate the corresponding phenomena: inflationary expectations - inflation itself, expectations of monetary reform - monetary reform, devaluation expectations - a fall in the exchange rate, expectations of economic crises - the crises themselves. thus, inflation expectations and other phenomena are associated with inflation, described and classified in the theory of negative economic assessments proposed by the author. inflation, like money circulation, is a complex economic category that can be characterized by a set of simpler parameters, which is reflected in the set of models of inflation proposed by the author.

References

1. Макконел К., Брю С. Экономикс: М.: республика, 1995. с. 163.
2. Большой экономический словарь. / Под ред. а.н. азрилияна. 6-е изд. М.: институт новой экономики, 2004. с. 343.
3. Современный финансово-кредитный словарь. / Под общ. ред. М.Г. Лапусты. – 2-е изд., доп. М.: инфра–М, 2002. с. 170.
4. Mirzaeva M.N. Formation of the concept and technology of intercultural competition among students in universities. International scientific journal "Scientific Horizons" No.5 / 2018- P. 81-84p
5. Mirzaeva M.N. Technology forming professional competence of students of the technical university in the lessons of foreign languages // International scientific journal "Scientific Horizon" No. 8/2019 -27-31s.
6. Mirzayeva M. N., Xasanov S., Goziyev A. Communicative competence as a component of the professional competence of a technical specialist //Актуальные вопросы современной науки. – 2021. – С. 10-12.

7. Mirzaeva M. N., Xasanov S. A new methodology for teaching a foreign language in technical universities for the development of student competence //Наука и Техника. Мировые Исследования. – 2020. – С. 9-10.

8. Mirzaeva M. N. Formation of concept and technologies of cultural competence at students of technical universities //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 907-909.